

Cynoglossum zeylanicum- A traditional folk medicine from Northeast India upholds the expression of Ihh in mice's fetal maternal tissue (D1 – D5)

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Cynoglossum zeylanicum (Lehm) belonging to the family Boraginaceae is found in great abundance in the Eastern Himalayas. Certain communities of north east India traditionally use the root bark of this wild herb to treat recurring abortion in women as well as to attain successful pregnancy. The present research work has been undertaken for in vivo validation of this herbal extract's effects on genomic translation in uterus of pregnant mice. Indian Hedgehog (Ihh) is an important member of the hedgehog gene family and is a progesterone regulated factor which is produced in the uterine epithelium and control stromal function via paracrine mechanism. It has been hypothesized that the crude root bark extract of *Cynoglossum zeylanicum* activates the Ihh expression during early gestation and facilitate successful pregnancy. Effect of *Cynoglossum zeylanicum* on fetal maternal-tissue has been studied histologically and localized in situ Ihh translational level using immunofluorescence tag in uterine tissue during the early gestation. The dry root bark powder was suspended in methanol for cold extraction. The crude extract was orally administered at the dose of 500mg/kg body weight/day to the female mice during Day 1 to Day4 of gestation. The treated females' uteri showed profound proliferation of luminal epithelium and glandular epithelium. Ihh has been localized in the uterine tissue in a spatio-temporal manner during the study period. The result indicates that the extract induces cellular proliferation during this critical phase of endometrial receptivity. Moreover, Ihh showed its expression during early gestation period which is necessary for successful pregnancy.

Keywords: Cynoglossum zeylanicum, Ihh, Histomorphology, Immunofluorescence.